

Galaxy Community

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ELIXIR-ITALY All Hands Meeting 2023
November 27-28, 2023

Outline

- Introduction
- Laniakea
- UseGalaxy.it
- Conclusions

The Galaxy Project logo, consisting of a stylized icon of three horizontal bars (two dark grey, one yellow) to the left of the word "Galaxy" in a large, bold, dark grey font, with the word "PROJECT" in a smaller, spaced-out, dark grey font below it.

Galaxy

PROJECT

Galaxy is a workflow manager developed to facilitate the interaction with bioinformatics tools and the handling of large biological datasets by users without specific IT expertise.

Through a coherent work environment and a **user-friendly web interface** it organizes data, tools and workflows providing **reproducibility, transparency** and **data sharing** functionalities to users.

galaxyproject.org

Galaxy BioHackathon 2020 | Analyze Data | Workflow | Visualize | Shared Data | Admin | Help | User | Using 1.0 GB

Tools

search tools

test

- SPAdes genome assembler for regular and single-cell projects
- Trimmomatic flexible read trimming tool for Illumina NGS data
- PopPUNK (cluster) Cluster bacterial genomes
- Trim Galore! Quality and adapter trimmer of reads
- MentalIST MLST Analysis
- MentalIST Distance Matrix
- MentalIST Tree
- Convert, Merge, Randomize BAM datasets and perform other transformations
- Bowtie2 - map reads against reference genome
- Map with Bowtie for Illumina
- FastQC Read Quality reports

WORKFLOWS

All workflows

Bowtie2 - map reads against reference genome (Galaxy Version 2.3.4.3+galaxy0)

☆ Favorite | Options

Is this single or paired library

Single-end

FASTA/Q file

No fastqsanger, fastqsanger.gz, fastqsanger.bz2 or fasta dataset available.

Must be of datatype "fastqsanger" or "fasta"

Write unaligned reads (in fastq format) to separate file(s)

Yes No

--un/--un-conc (possibly with -gz or -bz2); This triggers --un parameter for single reads and --un-conc for paired reads

Write aligned reads (in fastq format) to separate file(s)

Yes No

--al/--al-conc (possibly with -gz or -bz2); This triggers --al parameter for single reads and --al-conc for paired reads

Will you select a reference genome from your history or use a built-in index?

Use a built-in genome index

Built-ins were indexed using default options. See `Indexes` section of help below

Select reference genome

A. mellifera 04 Nov 2010 (AmeL4.5/apiMel4) (apiMel4)

If your genome of interest is not listed, contact the Galaxy team

Set read groups information?

History

search datasets

1 shown

1.83 MB

1: Bowtie2 on data 4: alignments

1.8 MB

format: bam, database: sacCer3

Job 'galaxy-chronos-275' finished successfully

25000 reads; of these:

25000 (100.00%) were unpaired; of these:

24999 (100.00%) aligned 0 times

0 (0.00%) aligned exactly 1 time

1 (0.00%) aligned >1 times

0.00% overall alignment rate

[bam_sor]

display at UCSC main test

display with IGV local

display in IGB View

Binary bam alignments file

Galaxy BioHackathon 2020 | Analyze Data | Workflow | Visualize | Shared Data | Admin | Help | User | Using 1.0 GB

Galaxy version 20.05

Server

Data Types

Data Tables

Display Applications

Jobs

Workflow Invocations

Local Data

User Management

Users

Groups

Roles

Forms

Tool Management

Install and Uninstall

Manage Metadata

Manage Whitelist

Manage Dependencies

Manage Dependencies (legacy)

View Lineage

View Migration Stages

View Error Logs

invesc(pv:vs480)

Search All | Installed Only

6035 repositories available at <https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/>

Name	Owner	Downloaded	Updated
bowtie2	devteam	>19k	today

bowtie2

Bowtie2: Fast and sensitive read alignment

Bowtie is an ultrafast and memory-efficient tool for aligning sequencing reads to long reference sequences. It is particularly good at aligning reads of about 50 up to 100s or 1,000s of characters to relatively long (e.g. mammalian) genomes. Bowtie 2 supports gapped, local, and paired-end alignment modes. Bowtie 2 outputs alignments in SAM format, enabling interoperability with a large number of other tools.

Show additional details and dependencies.

Revision	Tools and Versions	Requires	Tests	
25	bowtie2 2.3.4.3+galaxy0	+18.01	✓	Uninstall
24	bowtie2 2.3.4.3	+18.01	✓	Install
23	bowtie2 2.3.4.2	+18.01	✓	Install
21	bowtie2 2.3.4.1	+17.01	✓	Install

- Tools graphical user interface.
- Workflow graphical user interface
- The Toolshed: an "App store" for all Galaxy instances

The Galaxy Community

Goal of the community: to foster the use and development of Galaxy, focusing on making it easier to import data into Galaxy instances, helping to develop and share Galaxy tools and workflows, and facilitating the provisioning of Galaxy for service providers.

Main involvements of ELIXIR-Italy in the wider ELIXIR Galaxy community:

- Galaxy Implementation Plan: [Expanding the Galaxy: meeting \(the needs of\) ELIXIR Communities](#) (ended May 2023).
- Galaxy developers Monthly Meeting: 2nd Monday of the month, 10 am CET.
- HE Project EuroScienceGateway: create a distributed cross-european computing network, accessible through Galaxy.

Galaxy deployments fit-for-purpose

Small scale Galaxy servers, tailored to users needs.

Specific usage scenarios, e.g. development, training and privacy concerns.

Exploits cloud compute resources.

Security

Development

Training

Large scale, general purpose, National Galaxy instance(s).

Straight usage, just registration needed to exploits thousands tools.

(European) wide distributed computing network.

Exploits Cloud and HPC resources from different providers

Laniakea

Laniakea

LANIAKEA IS A CLOUD BASED GALAXY INSTANCE PROVIDER.

<https://laniakea-elixir-it.github.io/>

- Fully developed by ELIXIR-ITALY
- No need for the end user to know the underlying infrastructure.
- No need for maintenance of the hardware and software infrastructure.

Recommended for scenarios where users need full administrative control over a private Galaxy instance.

Laniakea

The Laniakea Dashboard home page.

Each tile provides a quick explanation of the application and links to the configuration and launch section.

Laniakea

elixir Laniakea Dashboard Deployments Advanced External Links Users elixir-Italy Marco Tangaro

Galaxy

Description: Deploy Galaxy on a single Virtual Machine from a VM image (FAST). The basic configuration includes CentOS 7, the selected Galaxy flavour, companion software and reference data. Configure, click on the 'Submit' button, wait for the confirmation e-mail(s) and log in to your new Galaxy instance. If after some hours you do not receive any e-mail please be sure to check your SPAM BOX.

Deployment description
description

Virtual hardware **Galaxy** Advanced

Instance flavour
Medium (2 cpu, 4 GB RAM, 20 GB disk)
CPUs, memory size (RAM), root disk size

Storage volume size
50 GB
Select storage size

Enable encryption
Off
Encrypt instance external storage

Submit Cancel

© 2019 ELIXIR-ITALY Laniakea
Laniakea has been developed in the framework of the INDIGO-Datacloud project funded by the European Commission Horizon research and innovation program under grant agreement RA 653549.

elixir Laniakea Dashboard Deployments Advanced External Links Users elixir-Italy Marco Tangaro

Galaxy

Description: Deploy Galaxy on a single Virtual Machine from a VM image (FAST). The basic configuration includes CentOS 7, the selected Galaxy flavour, companion software and reference data. Configure, click on the 'Submit' button, wait for the confirmation e-mail(s) and log in to your new Galaxy instance. If after some hours you do not receive any e-mail please be sure to check your SPAM BOX.

Deployment description
description

Virtual hardware Galaxy **Advanced**

Galaxy administrator e-mail
ma.tangaro@gmail.com
Type a valid e-mail address.

Galaxy administrator password
Enter your secret
Type a valid administrator password.

Galaxy version
Galaxy release 21.09
Galaxy release 20.05 recommended

Instance description
ELIXIR-ITALY
Set Galaxy Brand

Galaxy flavours
Galaxy minimal
Load Galaxy tools preset

Warning! You have not filled some mandatory fields. Please check the red boxes in each tab.

Submit Cancel

© 2019 ELIXIR-ITALY Laniakea
Laniakea has been developed in the framework of the INDIGO-Datacloud project funded by the European Commission Horizon research and innovation program under grant agreement RA 653549.

The web front-end provides different tabs for configuring the virtual hardware and the Galaxy instance (e.g administrator credentials).

Laniakea main features

Galaxy flavors - Deploy Galaxy with sets of tested, validated and pre installed tools, named Galaxy flavors.

Current available tools presets: Galaxy Minimal, Galaxy CoVaCS, Galaxy GDC Somatic Variant, RNA Workbench, Galaxy Epigen, Covid-19.

More Applications - No more limited to Galaxy. Jupyter Notebooks, RStudio and IRIDA available.

Environment with NextFlow, CWLtool and other development tools available.

Laniakea main features

Storage Encryption - Data privacy is provided through storage encryption "on-demand". Cloud administrators can't access your data, improving the GDPR compliance of the service.

Secrets Management - Users credentials safely stored encrypted.

VPN isolated environments - Automatic deployments of virtual environments on private networks.

Nobody can access Galaxy from internet.

User authentication to the VPN using the same Laniakea credentials.

Laniakea

The work on Laniakea still continue improving not only functionalities but also the interface.

- 1) Application portfolio
- 2) Applications form
- 3) Applications list
- 4) SSH Keys management

Laniakea@ReCaS

The ELIXIR-ITALY Laniakea@ReCaS Call offers access to Cloud resources to be used for the deployment of on-demand Galaxy instances, ready for production, with reference data and tools already pre-configured and ready to be used.

A scientific and technical evaluation board appointed by ELIXIR-ITA will assess the scientific soundness and technical feasibility of applications.

Projects are evaluated with a “first come, first served” policy until the total available resource annual budget will be assigned.

A new version of Laniakea@ReCaS will be soon available with the last revision of Laniakea, able to support more use cases.

Paper
Laniakea@
ReCaS

UseGalaxy.it

UseGalaxy.*

The screenshot shows the Galaxy Europe interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'Analyze Data', 'Workflow', 'Visualize', 'Shared Data', 'Help', 'Login or Register', and 'Using 0 bytes'. On the left, a 'Tools' sidebar lists various categories like 'GENERAL TEXT TOOLS', 'GENOMIC FILE MANIPULATION', and 'COMMON GENOMICS TOOLS'. The main content area features a 'COVID-19 research!' banner with a quote from Prof. Stephen Hawking and a 'News' section with several articles. A 'History' panel on the right shows an empty state with a message: 'This history is empty. You can load your own data or get data from an external source'. A blue 'OPEN CHAT' button is visible at the bottom right.

This block contains a collage of five Galaxy instance screenshots. From top-left to bottom-right: 1. 'Galaxy / ELIXIR-ES' showing a 'Welcome to usegalaxy.fr' message. 2. 'Galaxy / NELS' showing a 'Welcome to usegalaxy.fr' message. 3. 'Galaxy France' showing a 'Welcome to usegalaxy.fr' message. 4. 'Galaxy @ Belgium' showing a 'Welcome to usegalaxy.fr' message with logos for elixir, Vlaanderen, and fwo. 5. 'Galaxy' showing a 'Welcome to UseGalaxy CZ' message with the e-INFRA CZ logo and text indicating it's part of the e-infra.cz infrastructure.

Goal: ensure reproducible analyses across Galaxy instances.

National Galaxy instances:
EU, Fr, Be, No, Es, Cz and IT

The screenshot displays the UseGalaxy.it web interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Galaxy ITALY', a home icon, and menu items for 'Workflow', 'Visualize', 'Shared Data', 'Admin', 'Help', 'User', and a notification bell. The main content area is titled 'FastQC Report' for the file 'Sc_IP_fastq', dated 'Tue 12 Sep 2023'. It features a 'Summary' section with a list of quality metrics, each with a status icon (green checkmark or yellow warning triangle). A 'Basic Statistics' table is also present, showing key metrics like total sequences and bases. The right sidebar shows a 'History' panel with a search bar and a list of recent jobs, including 'FastQC on data 7: RawData' and 'Webpage'.

Measure	Value
Filename	Sc_IP_fastq
File type	Conventional base calls
Encoding	Sanger / Illumina 1.9
Total Sequences	1000000
Total Bases	48 Mbp
Sequences flagged as poor quality	0
Sequence length	48

The deployment of UseGalaxy.it is supported through PNRR ELIXIRxNextGenIT and Horizon Europe EuroScienceGateway projects

Usegalaxy.it (dev) currently deployed on Cineca AdaCloud resources.

The production instance will be deployed at ReCas-Bari data center.

This instance is already available to offload jobs to GARR Cloud and CINECA Cloud resources.

The infrastructure automation framework and documentation are hosted on Github:

- Usegalaxy-it test instance: <https://usegalaxy-it.ext.cineca.it>
- Usegalaxy-it github repository: <https://github.com/usegalaxy-it>
- Usegalaxy-it installation documentation: <https://usegalaxy-it.github.io/documentation/>

EuroScienceGateway leverages a distributed computing network across 13 European countries, accessible via at least 6 national Galaxy instances, facilitating access to compute and storage infrastructures across Europe as well as to data, tools, workflows and services that can be customized to suit researchers' needs.

Enable Nextflow and CWL job submission on the distributed computing network

<https://galaxyproject.org/projects/esg/>

Future outlook

The ELIXIR ITALY Galaxy community is focusing on providing **complementary** solutions for using Galaxy (and beyond) to its users.

Laniakea@ReCaS update and operation resume is scheduled for end 2023 - start 2024

UseGalaxy.it beta phase is scheduled for early 2024.

Thanks for your attention

CONTACTS:

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Backup

Data

Genomic data are distributed across several sequencing centres and/or IT infrastructures

Data volume growing not only in quantity but also on variety!

Data growth at EMBL-EBI Source: Charles E. Cook et al. Nucl. Acids Res. 2020; Volume 48, Issue D1, Pages D17-D23

Discipline	Data size	# devices
HEP-LHC	15PB/year	1
Astronomy	15PB/year	several
Genomics	0.4TB/genome	>1000

GDPR

The GDPR explicitly recognizes the sensitive nature of the collected genetic data (Article 9), but at the same time permits sensitive genetic data processing for scientific research purposes (Article 89(1)), provided this is allowed by EU or Member States law framework and appropriate safeguards measures are in place.

The screenshot shows the Galaxy BioHackathon 2020 interface. The main tool is Bowtie2, configured for a single-end library. The FASTA/Q file field is empty, with a message indicating no files are available. The interface includes a left sidebar with tool categories, a top navigation bar, and a right sidebar with a history panel. The history panel shows a job titled '1: Bowtie2 on data 4: alignments' with a size of 1.8 MB. The job status is 'finished successfully'. The output is displayed in a green box with the following details:

```

format: bam, database: sacCer3
Job 'galaxy-chronos-275' finished successfully
25000 reads; of these:
25000 (100.00%) were unpaired; of these:
24999 (100.00%) aligned 0 times
0 (0.00%) aligned exactly 1 time
1 (0.00%) aligned >1 times
0.00% overall alignment rate
[bam_sor
display at UCSC main test
display with IGV local
display in IGB View
Binary bam alignments file
  
```

- Tools graphical user interface.
- Input and output data management.
- Output visualization.
- Data and analysis parameters sharing.
- Used tools and parameters configuration always available -> **analysis reproducibility.**
- Reference data already available for many tools.

Galaxy Workflow Editor

Graphical user interface to easily add, connect and configure tools for composing workflows.

Galaxy BioHackathon 2020 Analyze Data Workflow Visualize Shared Data Admin Help User Using 1.0 GB

Galaxy version 20.05

Server

Data Types

Data Tables

Display Applications

Jobs

Workflow Invocations

Local Data

User Management

Users

Groups

Roles

Forms

Tool Management

Install and Uninstall

Manage Metadata

Manage Whitelist

Manage Dependencies

Manage Dependencies (legacy)

View Lineage

View Migration Stages

View Error Logs

javascript:void(0)

bowtie2

Search All Installed Only

6035 repositories available at <https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/>

Name	Owner	Downloaded	Updated
bowtie2 Bowtie2: Fast and sensitive read alignment	devteam	>19k	today

Bowtie is an ultrafast and memory-efficient tool for aligning sequencing reads to long reference sequences. It is particularly good at aligning reads of about 50 up to 100s or 1,000s of characters to relatively long (e.g. mammalian) genomes. Bowtie 2 supports gapped, local, and paired-end alignment modes. Bowtie 2 outputs alignments in SAM format, enabling interoperability with a large number of other tools.

Show additional details and dependencies.

Revision	Tools and Versions	Requires	Tests	
25	bowtie2 2.3.4.3+galaxy0	+18.01	✓	Uninstall
24	bowtie2 2.3.4.3	+18.01	✓	Install
23	bowtie2 2.3.4.2	+18.01	✓	Install
21	bowtie2 2.3.4.1	+17.01	✓	Install

Galaxy ToolShed

Serves as an "app store" to all Galaxies worldwide.

It is a **free service** Galaxy developers to share tools.

Galaxy Administrator can install tools on their instances.

All Galaxy users can access to the tools available on a server.

Allowing the community to move from command line tools to web user interfaces.

Allowing multiple users to exploit homogenous software environments, enhancing reproducibility.

Laniakea

ELIXIR-Italy partners are actively involved in the service development and/or also contribute with cloud resources.

A Laniakea service is in production for ELIXIR-ITALY partner but also for ELIXIR and external users.

The ELIXIR-ITALY **Laniakea@ReCaS** Call offers access to Cloud resources to be used for the deployment of on-demand Galaxy instances.

https://laniakea-elixir-it.github.io/laniakea_at_recas

Laniakea

elixir Laniakea Dashboard Deployments Users Documentation Marco Tangaro

Most used

Galaxy Galaxy

Galaxy Galaxy

Galaxy

All applications

Search...

Galaxy Galaxy

Galaxy cluster Galaxy

Galaxy

Full description

Deploy Galaxy from a VM image with cluster support (FAST). The basic configuration includes CentOS 7, SLURM, the selected Galaxy flavour, companion software and reference data. Configure, click on the "Submit" button, wait for the confirmation e-mail(s) and log in to your new Galaxy instance. If after some hours you do not receive any e-mail please be sure to check your SPAM BOX.

© 2019 ELIXIR-ITALY Laniakea

Laniakea has been developed in the framework of the INDIGO-Datacloud project funded by the European Commission H2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement RIA 663549.

The Laniakea Dashboard home page.

Each tile provides a quick explanation of the application and links to the configuration and launch section.

Soon more applications available: Jupyter, RStudio, ...

Different deployment strategies:

Live Build: build Galaxy from scratch -> always up-to-date (deployment time depending by the tools number).

Express: pre-built Galaxy images -> fast deployment, but tools not always at the last available version.

Docker: fast deployment of new flavours.

The web front-end provides different tabs to configure your Galaxy.

Virtual hardware: CPU, RAM and Storage

A screenshot of the Laniakea Galaxy configuration web interface. The page has a dark header with the Laniakea logo, navigation links (Dashboard, Deployments, Users, Documentation), and a user profile (Marco Tangaro). The main content area is titled "Galaxy" and contains a description, an "Instance description" text field, tabs for "Virtual hardware" and "Galaxy", an "Instance flavour" dropdown menu (set to "Large (4 cpu, 8 GB RAM, 20 GB dsk)"), an SSH public key field, an "Enable encryption" toggle (set to "Off"), and a "Storage volume size" dropdown menu (set to "50 GB"). At the bottom are "Submit" and "Cancel" buttons. The footer contains copyright information for ELIXIR-ITALY Laniakea and social media icons.

The web front-end provides different tabs to configure your Galaxy.

Galaxy software: version, credentials, flavor and reference data.

The screenshot shows the 'Galaxy' configuration page in the Laniakea dashboard. The page has a dark header with navigation links: 'Laniakea Dashboard', 'Deployments', 'Users', and 'Documentation'. A user profile 'Marco Tangaro' is visible in the top right. The main content area is titled 'Galaxy' and contains a description box with instructions: 'Deploy Galaxy on a single Virtual Machine from a VM image (FAST). The basic configuration includes CentOS 7, the selected Galaxy flavour, companion software and reference data. Configure, click on the "Submit" button, wait for the confirmation e-mail(s) and log in to your new Galaxy instance. If after some hours you do not receive any e-mail please be sure to check your SPAM BOX.' Below this are several form fields: 'Instance description' (empty), 'Virtual hardware' and 'Galaxy' tabs (with 'Galaxy' selected), 'Galaxy version' dropdown (set to 'Galaxy release 19.05'), 'Instance description' (set to 'ELIXIR-ITALY'), 'Set Galaxy Brand' (empty), 'Galaxy administrator e-mail' (set to 'ma.tangaro@gmail.com'), 'Galaxy flavours' dropdown (set to 'Galaxy minimal'), and 'Reference data repository' dropdown (set to 'usegalaxy.org Galaxy reference data CVMFS repository'). At the bottom are 'Submit' and 'Cancel' buttons. The footer contains copyright information: '© 2019 ELIXIR-ITALY Laniakea' and 'Laniakea has been developed in the framework of the INDIGO-Datacloud project funded by the European Commission H2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement RIA 653549', along with the ELIXIR ITALY logo and social media icons.

My deployments Refresh + New deployment

Show 10 entries Search:

Instance name	Status	Creation time	Galaxy flavour	VM flavour	Endpoint	Actions
covid encrypt	CREATE_IN_PROGRESS	2020-05-28 10:40:00	galaxy-minimal	large		Delete
test AAI Miguel	CREATE_COMPLETE	2020-03-31 22:30:00	galaxy-minimal	large	http://90.147.170.140/galaxy	Delete

Showing 1 to 2 of 2 entries Previous 1 Next

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Laniakea main features

Dashboard - By hiding the technical complexity behind a user-friendly web front-end, Laniakea allows its users to configure and deploy “on-demand” Galaxy instances with a handful of clicks.

No need for the end user to know the underlying infrastructure.

No need for maintenance of the hardware and software infrastructure.

Shared reference data - Each instance comes with reference data (e.g. genomic sequences) already available for many species, shared among all the instances through the CERN-VM FileSystem .

Galaxy with cluster - allowing to instantiate Galaxy with dedicated Resource Manager, allowing to customize the number of the virtual nodes to be created and their configuration in terms of number CPU and RAM.

Laniakea main features

Galaxy flavors - Deploy Galaxy with sets of tested, validated and pre installed tools, named Galaxy flavors.

Current available tools presets: Galaxy Minimal, Galaxy CoVaCS, Galaxy GDC Somatic Variant, RNA Workbench, Galaxy Epigen, Covid-19.

More Applications - No more limited to Galaxy. Jupyter Notebooks, RStudio and IRIDA available.

Environment with NextFlow, CWLtool and other development tools available.

Laniakea architecture

- **Dashboard** - User friendly access to configuration and launch of a Galaxy instance
- **INDIGO-IAM** - Authentication and Authorization system
- **INDIGO-PaaS** - PaaS layer for Galaxy deployment
- Cloud Provider - ReCaS Bari
- **Persistent storage** with/without encryption
- **Hashicorp Vault** - secrets management
- **Reference data** availability with CERN-VM FS

Laniakea

Laniakea@ReCaS

Currently, some important Italian Institutions are using Laniakea for their daily work:

- Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli (2 internal Galaxy servers).
- Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Puglia e della Basilicata (2 internal Galaxy servers and 1 IRIDA instance).
- Ospedale Pediatrico Giannina Gaslini (public server).
- University of Milan (public Galaxy server and tools development).
- IBIOM-CNR (public Galaxy server and tools development).
- University of Turin (training)

... and counting.

